

To observe if varietal reactions to the disease differed, four replications of three recommended varieties, Nahng Prayah 132, RD13, and RD7, and of the local variety Khao Nang were randomly planted in the area in 1978 wet season. On the basis of the grain yield and the percentage of straighthead panicles, Khao Nang and Nahng Prayah 132 were more tolerant of straighthead disease than RD7 and RD13 (see table). To the authors' knowledge, this is the first report of straighthead symptoms in Southeast Asia. ■

Percentage of affected panicles and grain yield of 4 varieties as a measure of damage from straighthead disease (av of 4 replications). Nakornsrithamaraj Rice Experiment Station, Thailand.

Variety	Straighthead panicles ^a (%)	Grain yield ^a (g/m ²)
Khao Nang	16 a	294 a
Nahng Prayah 132	39 b	161 b
RD13	63 c	148 b
RD7	63 c	98 b

^a In a column, values followed by the same letter do not significantly differ at the 0.05% level.

Dirty panicle or glume discoloration of rice in Sierra Leone

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The dirty panicle or discolored glume syndrome of rice is found in practically all rice ecologic zones in Sierra Leone. The disorder may be limited to individual grains, but in severe cases almost the entire panicles, including the rachises, become discolored. When the disease strikes, yield losses may reach 50%.

Some fungi associated with the disorder were identified by the Commonwealth Mycological Institute, U.K., and locally from seed samples from an upland area near Rokupr. They were: *Helminthosporium oryzae*, *Leptosphaeria* sp., *Phoma sorghina*, *Diplodiella oryzae*, *Alternaria* sp., and *Fusarium* sp. Rice bugs that feed on grain also predispose the glumes to fungal infection.

Screening tests to determine varietal reactions to grain and glume discoloration

were conducted at a dryland site at Makassa, near the Rokupr Rice Research Station, in the 1977–78 wet season. Cultivars that had 10% or fewer affected grains were classed as resistant. They included IRAT8, M1069-1-2, M50-4-2-2,

M133-6-1-2, IAC47, and LAC23. Cultivars with 25% or more of their grains severely affected were classified as susceptible. They included IB96, IB100, Line 13d/R75 sel. 958, TOX C1-95-2-2-69-1, IAC5544, and Perola. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Insect resistance

Field reaction of rice varieties to leaf folder at various nitrogen levels

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The rice leaf folder *Cnaphalocrocis medinalis*, previously a minor rice pest in the Punjab, has lately become serious. In 1978 kharif, 16 varieties were screened for reaction to leaf folder at 6 nitrogen levels in 3 nitrogen variety trials: NVT 1 (short-duration varieties, 110 – 120 days), NVT 2 (medium duration, 135 – 145 days), and NVT 3 (aromatic varieties,

120 – 140 days).

In NVT 1, leaf folder infestation increased with increasing nitrogen level. Infestation was maximum in variety PR422 and minimum in Palman 579. In NVT 3, infestation did not increase consistently with increased nitrogen level. Damage was maximum in PR299B and minimum in PR106. In NVT 3, leaf folder infestation was significantly lower in plots that received less nitrogen. PR476 had maximum insect damage and PR484, minimum. Leaf folders generally preferred fine-grained, scented varieties to short and medium-duration, nonaromatic varieties. ■

Incidence of rice leaf folder on varieties at various nitrogen levels. Kapurthala, India, 1978.

Variety	Leaf folder-damaged leaves ^a (no./ 10 hills)						Mean
	0 kg N/ha	30 kg N/ha	60 kg N/ha	90 kg N/ha	120 kg N/ha	150 kg N/ha	
<i>NVT 1^b, short-duration varieties (110 – 120 days)</i>							
PR103	10.7	12.3	11.0	11.7	13.0	14.1	12.2
PR404	9.3	9.3	9.1	10.7	15.7	18.3	12.2
PR405	1.7	12.3	8.0	11.3	15.1	11.3	12.1
PR406	9.0	10.3	14.1	12.3	12.3	18.3	12.8
PR422	9.3	10.1	12.0	15.0	16.1	16.0	13.3
Palman 519	12.3	4.1	9.3	10.3	12.0	12.3	10.2
Mean	9.1	9.9	10.1	11.9	14.2	16.2	12.1
<i>NVT 2^c, medium-duration varieties (137 – 145 days)</i>							
PR106	1.0	1.0	8.7	7.5	6.0	10.7	6.8
PR299 A	1.3	4.0	8.5	10.0	11.3	8.3	8.2
PR299B	8.0	8.1	8.3	9.3	1.3	13.1	9.2
PR504	9.1	9.3	5.3	8.7	8.1	8.7	8.4
Jaya	5.7	7.8	9.5	9.0	5.3	8.0	7.6
Mean	1.5	6.2	8.1	8.9	1.7	9.9	8.0
<i>NVT 3^d, aromatic varieties (120 – 140 days)</i>							
PR214	11.0	14.3	28.1	33.1	38.0	42.3	28.0
PR431	10.7	12.0	23.1	21.1	34.1	41.3	25.0
PR416	18.0	21.3	21.0	29.0	32.3	41.1	28.2
PR484	10.3	14.0	11.1	19.0	34.1	39.3	22.5
Basmati 310	19.3	20.7	20.3	23.1	36.1	45.7	21.1
Mean	13.9	16.5	22.3	26.6	35.3	43.3	26.3

^a Mean of 3 replications. Observations recorded 80 days after transplanting (DT).

^b Plot size = 10.0 m². N applied in 3 equal splits at 4, 26, and 54 DT. Differences between varieties significant at 1%: LSD 0.05 = 3.1, LSD 0.01 = 4.4; between nitrogen levels, nonsignificant.

^c Plot size = 12.5 m². N applied in 3 equal splits at 4, 26, and 53 DT. All factors nonsignificant.

^d Plot size = 8.1 m². N applied in 3 equal splits at 5, 30, and 45 DT. Differences between varieties significant: LSD 0.05 = 3.8, LSD 0.01 = 5.5; between nitrogen levels, significant at 1%: LSD 0.05 = 5.5, LSD 0.01 = 7.3. Interaction nonsignificant.